

Simplified algorithm to evaluate single body utilizing state of art tool, FEA (finite element analysis)

Mohammed Zahid Saadoon¹, David I Adam²

1 Ashty Teaching hospital
Erbil, Kurdistan region, Iraq
mzsmaxillofacial@gmail.com
2 OSTEOOTECH UK LIMITED
London – UK
davidibrahamadam@gmail.com

Abstract

In many instances the medical and dental researchers facing a dilemma in following an algorithm to evaluate a new designs or modify another design or comparing 2 different or more designs. Mechanical engineering is an enormous branch with myriad concepts and gigantic structure. In this guideline we want to simplify the process for the academic researchers a well as the clinician to better incorporate the mechanical engineering concepts in the decision-making process about choosing and evaluating devices.

Keywords: Bone, Biomechanics, dental implants, strain, displacement Von mises stress, 1st principal train , second principal strain, 3rd principal strain, strain energy density.

Introduction

If you take a tiny piece of any material and built a large domain, then you can simplify the response at any point by evaluating these tiny pieces . the direction of strains and stresses in small pieces tend to be more calculatable. For matter of naming these tiny pieces are called elements and the connections is called nodes. For a rod of the current guideline with diameter of 5mm and Lenth of 200mm. Simply, we make the geometry into smaller pieces. we have volumetric mesh type used in FEA which is opposite to the STL meshes, where the representation is done on the surface

Figure 1 This is the used model to represent our algorithm

The Total nodes was 99748 and the total elements was 65663

Boundary conditions

In reality when you hold an object you do not need to think about gravity as it is an inherited and integral feature, but in numerical world you should define everything as the object will be represented as floating domains. The simplest form of the engineering models is a simple rod. In the digital world you can suppose any plane in the space to be non-movable non-deformable. If we suppose that one of the object ends are fixed non-deformable, we can apply a force to the other end. anything in the numerical world is absolute. We had applied 50 newtons to the other end and analyze the resulted graphs. A very important question regarding the results of the numerical simulation how much it is close to the results of the physical world? This question had been answered a long time ago. Boundary conditions are the inputs of the FEA. Material properties could be obtained from any source, the best source for materials properties is (<https://www.matweb.com/>)

Boundary condition is an engineering simplified description of the physical laboratory experiment setting description

Type of analysis

Load when applied when applied stresses inside the domain will result and strain will be ensued. If loads rate is extremely slow the analysis will be static. Otherwise, analysis will be dynamic

The results

Any FEA will have graphs that we understand the possible results of a certain loading condition. There are many criteria for evaluation. We want to introduce the most important criteria of evaluation and their sequence. Numerical simulation using a very engineering tool called FEA (finite element analysis) that is the state of art in mechanical engineering analysis.

Figure 2 The mesh used to test the model

This is the volumetric mesh of the 5mm diameter rod with length of 200 mm. There is enormous amount of the data that had been paved the way to reach an advanced current position of this analysis. In these lines, we

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want to summarize the algorithm of comprehending the results of single piece domain with the simplest boundaries

1st criteria to be checked is the displacement.

The result will be applied on the object with values in number are represented in colors

Figure 3 The value of the displacement are not changed but the distribution are un-practical

Figure 4 This is also not suitable legend

Figure 5 Color distribution is better to be nicely distributed

Figure 6 We had increased the applied force . this is no deformation

Figure 7 This is 5 times deformation

Figure 8 This is the true deformation

We should tune the legend distribution of the colors by comparing the stiffest models and least stiff model if there is more than one model. Deformation is better to be revealed to convey the idea. The strain then is sought to allocated where most of the deformation occurring

Figure 9 This is the strain of the model

Another criteria is the Von mises stress is the agreed criteria to predict failure after maximum loading is occurring.

Figure 10 This is the von mises stress

To unravel the site where fatigue could be anticipate, strain energy is sought

Figure 11 This is the strain energy density

To see where the expansion of the material is occurring the 1st principal stain is sought

Figure 12 This is the 1st principal strain

To seek where the compression is occurring we are seeking the 3rd principal strain

Figure 13 3rd principal strain

Region where shearing is occurring is better revealed utilizing the 2nd principal strain

Figure 14 This is the 2nd principal strain

Displacement field are necessary to compare between different models to know exactly how the body is deforming

Figure 15 X field of displacement

Figure 16 Y field of displacement

These are the suggested criteria to evaluate single body model with single base and single load at the other end. This is the suggested algorithm to evaluate the performance of a single body.

Author profile

Mohammed Zahid Saadoon BDS– FKHCMS (Maxillofacial Surgery). During 2014-2024 he was involved in many researches in biomechanics and biomechatronic. He developed many theories in maxillofacial traumatology, craniofacial growth and dental implantology. He developed a unique dental implant system. He has a special interest in mechanical engineering applications in the medical and dental specialties as well as in forensic medicine. He is now working as maxillofacial surgeon in Ashty teaching hospital, largest secondary referral centers in Soran discrete at Kurdistan region / Iraq.